

UDC: 621.39(075)**PROBLEMS AT BRIDGE CROSSINGS**

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Anatation: This article covers issues such as design of bridge crossings on highways, problems of bridge crossings, correct selection of bridge crossings, subsidence of bridge exits.

Keywords: *bridge, river, waste, industrial, grade, percentage, local, asphalt concrete, cement concrete, current repair.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, due to the shortage of road bitumen in our republic, bitumen is being imported from the neighboring republics of Russia, Kazakhstan, and Turkmenistan, and it is affecting the conditions on the roads. Our country is a world leader in the production of construction cement. If we take into account the fact that limestone, sand, and gravel products are local resources in our country, our cement-concrete roads are economical and we use cement developed by ourselves. Also, on October 2, 2019, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, at the meeting selector dedicated to the development of the road industry and the wide attraction of investments in this field, said that in the construction of highways, it is necessary to gradually switch to roads with cement concrete coating. , on the basis of international standards, the task of construction, reconstruction and capital repair of highways with the introduction of innovative technologies has been set.

[1.2]

MAIN PART

A large part (more than 95%) of the water-carrying structures built on highways and railways are pipes. They do not change the traffic conditions of cars, because they can be placed in any combination of road plan and profile.

pipelines do not narrow the carriageway and the side of the road, and also do not require changing the type of road surface. In addition, pipelines can be assembled from lightweight reinforced concrete and concrete elements, which allows the use of cranes with a small load capacity. Construction of bridges imposes greater demands on the longitudinal profile of roads. Placement of bridges on vertical and horizontal curves or large longitudinal slopes complicates their construction. Bridges sometimes have to use a different type of pavement than the roads leading to it; very high elevations, for example, when crossing deep ravines, even when water consumption is very low, leads to the construction of bridges with large spans, which makes bridge construction expensive; the fact that the bridges cross the water streams in a crooked way also creates difficulties. All the mentioned cases allow us to consider pipes as the main type of small structures that carry water in constant and periodic water flows. Bridges are built only in cases where the pipelines cannot pass all the water flowing to the road. In current road construction, reinforced concrete bridges and standard pipes consisting of prefabricated elements are most common in centralized enterprises. The main type of reinforced concrete pipes are unified (round and rectangular) pipes. They are used both on highways and railways. On low-grade roads in mountainous areas, pipes made of dry stone and brick are sometimes built at the work site. To increase the throughput of the structure without increasing the height of the riser, multi-hole pipelines consisting of several pipes laid side by side are built. Observations show that in these cases, water consumption is evenly distributed between pipes, but pipes with more than four holes are not economical. In these cases, it is advisable to build bridges. When carrying calculated flows, pipes should usually work in a non-pressurized mode, where the flow is in contact with air along the free surface along the entire length of the structure. As an exception, semi-pressure or pressure (entrance to the structure is buried) mode is allowed on highways, sometimes on city roads, in which structural measures must be taken

to ensure the stability of pipes and roadbed against water leakage. . When the water flows in a non-pressurized mode, the elevation of the upper point of the inner surface of the pipe above the water level should be such that it passes objects accidentally falling into the water, and in circular and dome-shaped pipes with a height of up to 3 m, it should be $\frac{1}{4}$ of the height of the pipe, the height and at least 0.75 m in pipes longer than 3 m; in rectangular pipes with a height of up to 3 m, it should be at least $\frac{1}{6}$ of the height of the pipe, and in pipes with a height of more than 3 m, it should be at least 0.5 m. Pipes with a hole diameter of at least 0.75 m are used on highways and city roads (at least 0.5 m in ditches at road exits). For ease of use, pipes with a hole diameter of at least 1.0 m are recommended for lengths of less than 20 m, and pipes with a hole diameter of at least 1.25 m for longer lengths[3].

Highways and railroads cross many rivers, streams, intermittent open water streams, and hydroelectric reservoirs. A system of structures is built to cross any water barrier, they are called open water crossings. Artificial structures that serve to cross the water flow itself include passages through the open water flow; access roads to artificial structures, these are usually built in the form of ground lifts, their slopes (slopes) are constantly or periodically washed by water; control and protection structures, they are artificial structures and are designed to protect access roads from the possibility of water flow damage. Man-made structures and the roads leading to them are the main transport structures of the waterway. Control and protection structures are usually called auxiliary structures because they do not directly carry cars or trains [4].

The bridge crossing is a component of the road, therefore, when designing it, it is necessary to take into account the main demand for excellent service for road freight. Choosing a place to cross the river

should be subject to this requirement. However, the bridge crossing consists of a complex of complex and expensive structures, the costs of their construction depend on the location of the crossing on the river [5]. In this regard, while crossing the river, it is sometimes necessary to divert the road from its shortest route, passing the road route from the most appropriate place. In these cases, the inevitable losses in cargo transportation are compensated by the savings achieved in the construction and maintenance of the bridge crossing. When designing a bridge passage, it is necessary to ensure its sufficient carrying capacity, which is determined by the width of the passage on the bridge or the number of roads and the corresponding load carrying capacity of all structures. In order to allow cars or trains to pass easily, it is necessary to have an appropriate profile and plan of the road when crossing the river, including at the borders of the roads that come to the bridge and flood.

CONCLUSION

As of today, the condition of bridge crossings in our country is deteriorating. This situation exists in other countries as well. This is due to the fact that the materials of the shore support and the bridge beams are different, and subsidence is occurring at the bridge crossing.

In order to prevent the subsidence of bridge crossings, if we lay a cement concrete coating for the base part at a distance of 3 m from the bridge support, we will prevent subsidence and ensure the uniformity of the transition to the bridge with our road..

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